

MAIN ASPECTS OF ORGANIZING FOOTBALL COURSES IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: In the article, the author studied and analyzed the main aspects of the organization of football training sessions in educational institutions.

Key words: Football, ball, action games, game elements, training, preparation, walking, referee.

INTRODUCTION

Modern football appeared in Uzbekistan at the beginning of the last century and became one of the most popular sports in a short time. Its developed areas were Fergana, Tashkent, Andijan, Kokan and Samarkand. Football was played for the first time in Fergana. At the end of 1911, the first football team was formed here.

The number of football teams formed in Fergana in August 1912 was added to the "football team". After some time, they started playing football in different regions of Tashkent region and Shari. After gaining independence in our country, more and more attention is being paid to physical education and sports. Our athletes have achieved good results in Asian and world competitions and are raising the flag of Uzbekistan high. The services of our President in the achievements achieved in the field of sports in recent years are great. Regular development of physical education and sports is always in the eyes of the President and the state.

Planning is one of the most important elements of managing the training process in order to improve technical and tactical training of young football

players. High-level results in modern football determine the need to regularly search for a form of training young players. Modern football makes high demands on the personality and preparation of young players. It is necessary to find more advanced, perfect organizational forms, methods and means of preparation. This, in turn, requires a high level of knowledge and skills from the coach, a scientific approach to sports training.

Most organizations are involved in football, such as schools, colleges, institutes, industrial organizations and the military. Each team uses all its knowledge and capabilities to achieve the best result. At the heart of the game is the struggle of two United teams for the victory of all players. During the football game, each player has the opportunity to show his personal qualities and, at the same time, his physical qualities, but at the same time, the game focuses on the individual and collective aspirations of each player towards a common goal. 'requires clarification.

Those who play football must know technical and tactical methods perfectly, be able to use these methods in complex game situations, and act in coordination with all members of the team.

Teaching the elements of football can begin with elementary school students. The guys master the technique of moving the ball with repeated repetitions of the exercises. Like other sports, playing football is based on the game form of training. The content of the lessons effectively combines game exercises and relays, outdoor games and sports exercises. The content of the lessons combines a number of didactic principles, among which the principles of access and individual approach play an important role, because it is very difficult for young children to master sports games. An individual approach is achieved by choosing the methods of teaching and training, depending on the level of mastery of the educational material by each child, as well as taking into account the reaction of his body to the given physical load. Technical training is carried out gradually, by

complicating the conditions for performing movements.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Sports games, first of all, are aimed at strengthening health, improving the general physical fitness of children, and satisfying their biological need for movement. The main goal of sports games is to introduce children to sports games based on the correct technique. But in no case should it become a highly specialized training, preparation for participation in competitions. Real competitions where the fight for points and places is an unbearable psychological burden for a child. A distinctive feature of sports games is their emotion. A positive emotional tone is an important condition for health, it prevents various diseases and physical fitness. maintains interest in exercise.

Imitation of learned motor movements. Directly studied motor behavior, which is carried out under light conditions. Such exercises are especially important when learning new motor movements associated with the possibility of falls and injuries. The studied motor movement itself was performed in slow motion. When performing the physical exercise in slow motion, it is easier for the child to control his movements and he makes fewer mistakes. More complex movements of sports games can be studied in specially created conditions (outside the game). At the same time, it is desirable to direct the child's attention to the quality of movement.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the process of teaching sports exercises and games, it is important to ensure conscious mastering of movements. Understanding the meaning of actions by children accelerates the process of skill formation, increases the ability to independently choose effective actions and use them appropriately in the course of further movement. A child's conscious and active attitude to actions appears only when he knows why it is appropriate to use certain actions in a certain situation, to carry them out in a certain direction. But for this, it is not enough for

the teacher to explain and demonstrate the movements in stereotyped exercises - it is necessary to create conditions for using the learned movements in various motor movements. Creative activity manifests itself only when children learn to freely use actions independently in different situations. Children should be encouraged to be creative.

Teaching young children to play football should be divided into three stages: preparatory, basic and final.

The main tasks at the preparatory stage: increase general physical fitness; increase general endurance; improvement of running technique; improving health and, first of all, the functioning of the cardiovascular system and respiratory system. Implementation of this stage is carried out in children's daily life during outdoor games and physical exercises for walks, during children's independent movement activities, direct physical education and sports entertainment. This stage can last from several months to half a year or more

The main stage is the stage of directly learning to play football. The main and most effective form of teaching children to play football is "fun ball", "young player" or It is advisable to conduct it in the form of "ball school" and "health club". Also, elements of football can be included in the physical education curriculum during the school year. The duration of such training is 25-30 minutes. The existence of a three-part lesson form (introductory, main, final) allows the teacher to rationally distribute teaching and learning materials.

Health, educational and educational tasks are defined for each lesson.

The introductory part is a warm-up, the purpose of which is to prepare the child's body for intensive work in the main part of the lesson. The content of the introduction can include various types of walking (on the toes, on the heels, on the outside of the foot, rolling from the heel to the side of the foot, with high knees, with the back of the lower leg covered, with cotton under the knee, etc.). (in a column one by one, with recovery in pairs, "snake", diagonally, running in

combination with other movements, looking backwards, turning around the signal, etc.), as well as jumping, jumping, breathing exercises and open o games. For older children, the duration of the introduction is up to 3-4 minutes. Thus, the exercises in the introductory part of the lesson are leading exercises to learning the movements in the main part of the lesson. The content of the main part of the lesson is different. It starts with a small set of general development exercises or open games. In this part of the lesson, stronger exercises are combined with less intensive exercises, which ensures an optimal level of physical and mental load in an older child.

Movements are energetic, fast, require endurance, and also increase the functional state of the body. A complex of general development exercises can be learned and performed in 4-5 sessions, no more. Coordinated implementation of previously learned and mastered movements allows the child to prepare for the development of a new load on the body, and the teacher - the most rational and effective distribution of his forces in performing the main types of movements. Practice shows that when teaching children the technical basics of playing football, it is appropriate to use exercises called training, i.e. movements similar in structure to the main elements of a certain movement technique. For example, when learning to hit the ball with the inside of the foot, the imitation exercise of the same movement can become a leader; when learning to stop the ball with the base - turning the ball back and forth with the base, standing in one place, etc. Children perform exercises with their right and left feet in football. it is necessary to ensure their development and not to limit their creativity. And this aspect is achieved when the child knows when and under what conditions he can apply the acquired skills and abilities.

The duration of the main part is up to 20 minutes.

Thus, the main part of the lesson is varied and exciting in content, which allows the teacher to perform the assigned tasks. In the final part of the lesson, it

is necessary to bring the child's body to a relatively calm and even position. The following will help: walking together with breathing exercises, exercises for relaxation and relaxation, quiet games, etc. The final part lasts 4-5 minutes. The final stage is the stage of improving the technical, elementary tactical skills of playing football, that is, the football match itself. The duration of the football competition with children is 25 minutes, including a 5-minute break for rest and relaxation. Before each game, it is necessary to warm up, consisting of exercises familiar to children. It is appropriate to include a football competition between two teams of older children, consisting of one or two groups of children, in the program of Health Day, sports holiday, joint sports and leisure activities with parents. All training in this phase is done outdoors.

Children should know the basic rules of playing football:

- before the start of the game, a draw is made to select or start the sides. The ball is placed on the ground in the center of the field;

- the players of the team try to score as many goals as possible to the opponent's goal and after losing the ball, they defend themselves in accordance with the rules of the game;

- football;

- a game of two teams and each team has up to 5-7 players, one of them is the captain;

- compliance with the rules of the game and the duration of the game are controlled by the referee;

- if the ball has crossed the full line, it is considered to be in the goal and all the rules have been observed during the game;

- in football, players perform all movements with the ball with their feet;

- the goalkeeper and the throwing player have the right to receive the ball;

- Football is a team game, and despite the spirit of competition and the desire to win, the players treat each other with respect.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the sports game football has great educational value, regular use of the game improves motor skills and ensures the full development of movements, which primarily includes running, jumping and coordination. The game has a specific structure and methodology that the teacher must follow.

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